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Poetic Creation: A Unified Vision of Sri Aurobindo and Rabindranath Tagore

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Abstract

In most of the western theories, literature is a creation in implied sense. During 1920s, the dominance of material and somewhat deviance from emotion in the 'New Criticism' sometimes gives the impression of a literary work being a construction rather than creation of it. The great literary and philosophical figures of Indian Renaissance, Sri Aurobindo and Rabindranath Tagore advocated the assimilation of 'emotion and intellect' in literary works. Their perspective regarding poetic creation explores the Indian literary thought and tradition emphatically. Due to such distinctive principles, the vision of Sri Aurobindo and Rabindranath Tagore receives worldwide appreciation and occupy distinct place in literary realm. This paper seeks to glorify their contribution and strengthen the Indian knowledge system.

Keywords Assimilation Rupabhedah, Pramanani, Life-Dharma.

Introduction

The reservoir of western literary thinking lies in Greek thought especially in the propounded theories of the Triumvirate of Socrates, Plato and Aristotle. Though afterwards due to the vicious role of shifting power led to the dominance of one thought over another: Paganism was replaced by Judaism and Christianity. The Indian literary tradition finds its proliferation in the multilingual tradition derived from the classical Tamil, Pali, Prakrit and Sanskrit with the springhead in Indian Philosophy. The panoramic view of Indian literary tradition is reflected in the literary discussions of many Indian writers. The unified vision of Sri Aurobindo and Rabindranath Tagore regarding poetic creation explores the Indian literary thought and tradition emphatically.

Objective of study

This paper seeks to glorify their contribution and strengthen the Indian knowledge system.

Review of Literature

Poetry is a genre of literature which explores human personality emphatically and empowers an individual to raise voice against the prevalent inertia in an age; thereby transforming society. Sri Aurobindo is credited with creating a lineage in Indian English poetry which leads to spiritual and mystical poetry. Despite his western education and prolonged stay in England, he could not restrain his inclination towards *Vedas*, *Upanishads* and *Bhagwad Gita*. Hence his poetic ideology is inspired by Indian literary thought and tradition. Sri Aurobindo's views regarding poetic creation delineated in The Future Poetry present a distinct vision from his predecessors as their poems were merely the imitation of Romantic and Victorian poets which resulted into the expression of gratitude towards colonial rule. Sri Aurobindo's spiritual and mystical vision imparted a new insight to the concept of poetic creation. His firm faith in spirituality led him to visualize the future of Indian poetry in a distinct manner which is reflected in one of his letters:

At present many are turning to India for its sources of spirituality, but the eye has been directed only towards yoga and philosophy, not to the poetical expression of it. When the full day comes, however, it may well be that this too will be discovered, and then an

Indian who is at once a mystic and a true poet and able to write in English has in his mother tongue (that is essential) would have his full chance.”(Letters on Poetry, Literature and Art, 454)

Main Text

Sri Aurobindo's poetic ideology stems from Indian philosophy. He depicts poet as a seer and describes him as, “who creates out of himself and has the indefeasible right to follow freely the breath of the spirit within him, provided he satisfies in his work the law of poetic beauty (*The Future Poetry*, 41).” While describing the process of poetic creation in *The Future Poetry*, Aurobindo cautioned poets not to opt narrow approach because the poetic work depends primarily on the poet's knowledge and the collective consciousness contributes in flourishing the poetic idea. In his letters, Sri Aurobindo emphasized on the 'true spirit' as the prime element of poetry and encapsulated three bedrock elements in the composition of great poetry “a highest intensity of rhythmic movement, a highest interwoven verbal form and thought substance of style, and a highest intensity of the soul's vision of truth (18).” The poetic expression takes the form of mantra with the inclusion of these elements. Sri Aurobindo's firm belief in Indians attaining the spiritual state and expressing the supreme spiritual experience into speech is still the driving force for the entire humanity. A similar vision of Indian literary tradition and thought is highly perceptible in the works of Rabindranath Tagore but in a somewhat distinct manner.

In 1922, Tagore's non-fictional work entitled *Creative Unity* was published which represented his views regarding the poetic creation and appreciation of the aesthetic value of the literary works. Due to the distinctive principles, the great literary and philosophical figure of Indian Renaissance, Rabindranath Tagore received worldwide appreciation and attained distinct place in literary realm.

In most of the western theories, literature is a creation in implied sense. During 1920s, the dominance of material and somewhat deviance from emotion in the 'New Criticism' sometimes gives the impression of a literary work being a construction rather than creation of it. In an essay entitled “Wanted: an Ontological Critic”, Ransom made a formal announcement:

I suggest that the differentia of Poetry as a discourse is an ontological one. It treats an order of existence, a grade objectivity, which cannot be treated in scientific discourse... Poetry intends to recover the denser and more refractory original world which we know loosely through our perceptions and memories. By this supposition it is a kind of knowledge which is radically or ontologically distinct.(148)

In response to it, Rabindranath Tagore's view implies that literary work is a creation, not construction because construction fulfils only the need but creation expresses the personality of an individual. To impart an aesthetic sense to literary work, the prime requisite is the sense of 'totality'. The concept of 'totality' implies that literary work is a composite of innumerable forms which sustain its own place in the work perfectly. Each word constitutes the total meaning of the creative work and all forms contribute to the development of the basic idea. Such forms get significance due to assimilation in the work. Such concept of the 'totality' finds expression in *Creative Unity* as 'Rupabhedah'. All multiple forms, in their separateness must carry something that signifies “the paradox of their ultimate unity, otherwise there would be no creation”. Tagore takes up 'Pramanani' that signifies the dictum of mutual accommodation in the creation of aesthetic work. Thus 'Pramanani' or proportion proves relativity and connectivity in diverse forms. Rabindranath Tagore elucidates this idea creating the difference in the crowd of men and an army. Army imbibes the single idea and each soldier visualizes that singleness through his proportion of time, space and relative movement in march.

Rabindranath Tagore values the concept of freedom of creator and reader like western theorists but negates the idea of the sole domination of material without expressions. His concept is to keep the material in the background and continuously offer freedom to the expression. A similar view is expressed in *Comparative Literary Theory* by Prof. Kapil Kapoor:

The kumbhakara's creativity modulates one mode of reality into another- dravya into rupa etc.(without, of course, the destruction of dravya which alone is indestructible). Similarly, when the poet puts an experience/emotion into words, the experience continues to exist independent of the words and yet it appears inseparable from words.

Rabindranath Tagore proclaims that the success of any creative work lies in its freedom. To impart universal significance to individual idea, Rabindranath Tagore is in the favour of 'detachment' of the author. He elucidates the idea of freedom and the attainment of 'Parmanand' through this questionnaire of a poet and bird:

Where were your songs, my bird,
 when you spent your nights in the nest?
 Was not all your pleasure stored therein?
 What makes you lose your heart to the sky,
 The sky that is limitless?
 The bird answers:
 I had my pleasure while I rested within bounds.
 When I soared into the limitless, I found my songs!

Conclusion In Indian tradition, all worldly and spiritual pursuits serve a purpose and they contribute in the attainment of 'Purusarth', the ends of life-Dharma (righteousness), Artha (materialistic progress), Kama (satisfaction of desires), Moksha (liberation from sorrow). Thus, regarding the purpose of poetic creation both the great personalities Sri Aurobindo and Rabindranath Tagore advocated the assimilation of 'emotion and intellect' in poetic creation which result into the attainment of ultimate happiness. Such principles of Sri Aurobindo and Rabindranath Tagore regarding the aesthetic sense of poetic creation give them a paramount stand and present their unified vision about poetic creation.

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